

Great Temple Of Santa Cecilia

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The temple of Santa Cecilia is located in the current state of Mexico and was a significant religious center during the Postclassic period (1200-1521 AD), associated with the dominion of Tenayuca and controlled by the Mexica. However, materials have been found indicating that it was inhabited since the Classic period. Currently, only traces of the main temple remain alongside other places of worship. Currently, on the site, you can visit the Templo Mayor with a double staircase, a platform, and the on-site museum that houses one of the most important collections of monumental Aztec sculpture.

Date Range: 150 CE - 1521 CE

Region: Santa Cecilia Acatitlán

Region tags: Basin of Mexico, Mesoamerica, Mexico

Currently, Santa Cecilia Acatitlan is located within the municipality of Tlalnepantla, approximately 3 km northwest of Tenayuca. Today, it is surrounded by the population that carries the same name.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Solís, F., 1977, Catálogo de la Escultura Mexica del Museo de Santa Cecilia Acatitlán. Colecciones de los Museos. INAH, Mexico.
- Source 2: De Anda, M., 1980, Proyecto: Santa Cecilia Acatitlán, Edo de México. Informe entregado al Consejo de Arqueología del INAH, Archivo Técnico del Consejo de Arqueología, INAH.
- Source 3: Pareyón, E., 1966. "Museo de Santa Cecilia Acatitlán, Tlalnepantla", Boletín del INAH 23: 27-30

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL:
https://tesiunam.dgb.unam.mx/F/G8E98L2TJME12D4RBNC1IX4HTDB8X9Y9RIRFY1BIXMCMCIRNGFU-03192?func=full-set-set&set_number=018483&set_entry=000031&format=999

– Source 1 Description: Pareyón, E. 1963, Conservación del pueblo y de la Zona Arqueológica de Santa Cecilia Acatitlán. Bachelor thesis, UNAM, Mexico.

– Source 2 URL: https://mediateca.inah.gob.mx/islandora_74/islandora/object/guia:161

– Source 2 Description: García Moll, R., 1993, Santa Cecilia Acatitlan. Estado de México, INAH, Mexico.

– Source 3 URL: https://books.google.de/books?id=NZOEDWAAQBAJ&printsec=copyright&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false

– Source 3 Description: GARCÍA Moll, R. & R. Fierro Padilla (eds.), 2016, Arqueología de Santa Cecilia Acatitlán. antología. INAH, Mexico.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1922-1924, 1961

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Informe acerca del recorrido par las zonas arqueológicas de San Bartolo y Santa Cecilia, Estado de Mexico

Notes: Proyecto Santa Cecilia Acatitlán

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:
– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
– No

- ↳ One single feature
– Mound

- ↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

Notes: The site corresponds primarily to the discovery of the Templo Mayor, a building with a double staircase similar to those seen in Teopanzolco, Tlatelolco, Tenayuca, and Tenochtitlan. Additionally, platforms have been located, and in the adjacent grounds, now covered by houses and gardens, the remains of more stone-built structures have been recovered

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

- ↳ A group of features:
– I don't know

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: The site was destroyed, reused and buried

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Spanish Conquest

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

↳ In modernity

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: It was dedicated to Tlaloc and Huitzilopochtli.

Notes: It was dedicated to Tlaloc and Huitzilopochtli. In central Mexico, worship of these two deities took place during the Late Postclassic period. Tlaloc played a crucial role in agriculture, being the god of rain and fertility for the Mexicas. On the other hand, Huitzilopochtli was the deity of the sun, war, and the guardian god of the Mexicas.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– I don't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Field doesn't know

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main temple is the largest and is dedicated to the two main deities. In front there is a smaller platform, in addition to other studies, for example in Tenochtitlan, it is known that the South Temple was larger than the north temple (López Austin and López Luján 2009).

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 90

Notes: However, these data should be taken with caution, since only the main temple has been recovered.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 751.44

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They have not been completely excavated, so the limits are not fully delimited.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: The tezontle stones were worked to be able to be arranged in the building, and architectural nails with skull shapes were also found.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Sculptures of felines and snakes were found

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The remains of architectural nails in the shape of human heads

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Considering the similarities with the temples in central Mexico, it is believed that they were constructed to worship Tlaloc and Huitzilopochtli. Additionally, in a nearby temple that was destroyed in 1972, a sculpture of the goddess of vegetation was found (García Moll and Fierro Padilla 2016: 32).

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: It was a ceremonial site during postclassic period, but is currently not used for this purpose.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that some citizens of the town still go to the site to worship in memory of the site.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Notes: A mortuary lump was located in the periphery, but the location or what its function was is not specified.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Pareyón's descriptions (1966) refer to various objects such as animal heads made of stone, stone objects and ceramics, but do not refer to a particular context.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Other

– Other [specify]: The site is protected by the INAH, and the residents of Santa Cecilia are proud of their past, which allows its protection.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no data in this regard, but comparing with other sites with similar characteristics such as Tlatelolco and Tenochtitlan, it is possible that this was the case (García Moll and Fierro Padilla 2016: 137-143)

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unfortunately the space that has been excavated is smaller, but due to the characteristics it is possible

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Chimalpopoca codex refers to several nearby cities, but it does not seem to make a direct reference to this site.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Great Temple Of Santa Cecilia, López Austin, Alfredo, and Leonardo López Luján. Monte Sagrado-templo Mayor. El Cerro Y La Pirámide En La Tradición Religiosa Mesoamericana. Mexico City: IIA-UNAM/INAH, 2009.